

The Statistics of the Quantum Free Particle $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Jan. 9, 2024

We argue that Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) and quantum free particle statistics are both based on independent distribution. In the MB case, the quantity distributed is single particle kinetic energy, even in the presence of a potential $V(x)$. Collisions which create equilibrium are among single particles and involve their kinetic energies at any point x . $V(x)$ simply links $e(x_1)=p_1^2/2m$ to $e(x_2)=p_2^2/2m$. The equilibrium collisions still deal with a distribution of energy. One may note that energy is a conserved quantity and that $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$.

Quantum mechanics of a free particle is similar, we argue, but involves two separate distributions, $\exp(-iet)$ in time and $\exp(ipx)$ in space. Both of these follow the MB property $\exp(-e_1t)\exp(-ie_2t) = \exp(-i(e_1+e_2)t)$ and $\exp(ip_1x)\exp(ip_2x) = \exp(i(p_1+p_2)x)$. We consider two issues. First, we note that in the MB case, $V(x)$ changes $e=pp/2m$ at each x point, while in the quantum case $V(x)$ is a statistical average potential energy associated with stochastic hits. These hits are associated with spatial form $V(x)$ and so one uses $\exp(ipx)$ statistics. (We also consider two slit interference and reflection-refraction where again $\exp(ipx)$ statistics are used.) $\exp(ipx)$ is not only associated with impulse hits, but with detecting changes in space and so is used with $V(x)$ which changes in space. $\exp(-iet)$ on the other hand is linked with changes in time and so should be the statistics to use in the case of a purely time dependent perturbation as we consider (the Rabi case). We also investigate why e is associated with time and p with space. Thus, quantum mechanics often deals with resolution of time or space which in turn means different interactions at different time or x points and hence interference. If no resolution occurs, such as in the case of photon absorption/emission, one has a Maxwell-Boltzmann type of energy distribution with minimum information.

Conservation of a Distributed Quantity and Statistics

We have argued in previous notes and mention again here that Maxwell Boltzmann statistics and quantum free particles are both associated with the distribution of conserved quantities. In the MB case, one is interested in conserved energy (e.g. elastic collisions). One adds the extra condition of particle independence which requires the number of particles to go to infinite and leads to the information of a particle being strictly associated with its e (and the overall temperature T). In such a case,

$$P(e_1)P(e_2)=P(e_3)P(e_4) \text{ if } e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4 \text{ (i.e. there is complete independence) ((1))}$$

This immediately yields $p(e) = C\exp(-e/T)$ form and information as $\ln C - e/T$ ((2)).

In the quantum case, one has two distributed quantities e and p and they are treated separately. One may ask why this is the case. If one considers n -slit interference or diffraction from a single slit (with length scales equal to \hbar/p or so), then energy does not change, but impulse hits occur which change the direction, but not magnitude of p and lead to interference. Thus $\exp(ipx)$ is not simply a statistical quantity, but self-measures changes in space by interacting with such

changes (which lead to impulse hits at different x points) even if energy does not change. Usual reflection-refraction and one dimensional reflection-refraction are two other examples of cases for which energy remains constant, while p changes. Thus, experimentally there is evidence of different statistics, one involving e and one involving p. The statistics used seem to be associated to what one resolves in an interaction. For V(x), one resolves changes in x and so exp(ipx) is suitable, while for V(t), one resolves changes in t and exp(-iet) becomes important as in the Rabi case.

Thus, the statistics used to solve equilibrium type of problems are associated with distributed variables. In the MB case, e is the variable. For two slit interference or reflection-refraction, the p vector is the variable which changes, while for V(t), exp(-iet) is important.

One may ask why p should be associated r vector and e with time, as it is in the Lorentz invariant: $-Et + p \cdot r$ ((2))

One may note that both E and t are strictly scalars, while p and r are vectors. Furthermore, one may have energy (rest mass) without motion in space. Thus, energy must be associated with time, even if one ignores space, but p momentum requires some kind of motion in space. Given different p vectors, one is forced to consider differing orientations, hence p dot r. Energy without motion is associated only with t and continues to be so even if motion is introduced.

Consider for example a particle moving as a ray in a certain direction. It has (px,py,pz), but also energy= $p_x p_x / 2m + p_y p_y / 2m + p_z p_z / 2m$. Changes to px, py or pz lead to a change in orientation in space, but energy remains a scalar, and might not change in value at all. If it does, it changes in time because it is not a vector.

The Single Particle Quantum Bound State Versus the MB Case

The MB gas situation involves a distribution of energy due to collisions at each x. A particle at x1 which does not collide has energy $p_1 p_1 / 2m + V(x_1)$, while at x2 it has energy $p_2 p_2 / 2m + V(x_2)$ such that the two energies are the same. The potential transforms p and pp/2m in space.

In quantum mechanics, there is a natural length \hbar/p associated with a particle and it cannot be said to change in a dx much smaller than this length. In other words, it cannot resolve such a dx.

Thus, V(x) seems to be an average quantity. exp(ipx) detects changes in space by coupling with V(x) through $V(x) = \text{Sum over } k V_k \exp(ikx)$. As a result, one has a distribution of exp(ipx)s as well as a distribution of exp(ikx) which come into equilibrium by creating a constant average energy En at each x.

Formally, one may write an average kinetic energy KE(x) associated with an average potential energy V(x) i.e.

$$\{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) p p / 2m \} / \{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \} + V(x) = E_n \quad ((3))$$

If one multiplies by $\{ \text{Sum over } p a(p) \exp(ipx) \}$, one has a kinetic energy free particle distribution (first term on the LHS) and a combination of a V(x) distribution interacting with $\{ \text{Sum over } p$

$a(p)\exp(ipx)$ to create a potential energy term because $\exp(ipx)$ interacts with the potential. These two pieces yield a constant energy at each x .

One may ask why one does not use $\exp(-i p^2/2m t)$ to solve the problem. This statistics detects changes in time when it interacts, but $V(x)$ is strictly a function of x and so one cannot solve the problem using $\exp(-iet)$. One may, however, do the following. In principle, one has $\exp(-ipp/2m t) \exp(ipx) a(p)$ for each free particle probability. If person A chooses an origin $x=0$ at some point x_1 as viewed by person B, then:

$$\text{Person A } i\hbar d/dt W(t) / W(t) = E_n - V(0) \quad ((4)) \quad \text{or } W(t) = \exp(-i (E_n - V(0)) t)$$

Different person As choose different origins, so in general:

$$W(t) = \exp(-i (E_n - V(x)) t) \quad ((5))$$

((5)) describes the average kinetic energy at x , but does not solve for E_n . If one considers full energy, one has $W(t) = \exp(-i E_n t)$. If one knocks out a particle and finds its momentum is p , then $\exp(-ipp/2m t)$ is the time wavefunction because this single particle has the two kinds of statistics $\exp(-ipp^2/2m t)$ and $\exp(ipx)$.

The fully bound system has an average energy $\exp(-i E_n t)$ because one does not resolve any fine points of changes in time, but one has $\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ because one does resolve x points in $V(x)$.

$\exp(-iet)$ Statistics

To see $\exp(-iet)$ statistics come into play in quantum mechanics, one may consider a perturbation potential $V(t)$. Here we follow (1). Thus:

$$H = H_0 + V(t) \quad \text{where } H_0 W_n = E_n W_n \quad ((6))$$

$$i\hbar d/dt a(t) = (H_0 + V(t)) a(t) \quad \text{where } a(t) = \sum_n |n\rangle \langle n| a \quad ((7))$$

$$\text{Let } \langle n|a\rangle = a_n(t). \quad \text{Then } i\hbar d/dt a_n = E_n a_n + \sum_{n'} V_{nn'}(t) a_{n'} \quad ((8))$$

$$\text{Let } a_n(t) = \exp(-i E_n t) b_n(t) \quad ((9)) \quad \text{Then}$$

$$i\hbar d/dt b_n(t) = \sum_{n'} b_{n'} V_{nn'} \exp(i (E_n - E_{n'}) t) \quad ((10))$$

$$\text{Let } V_{nn'} = A_{nn'} \exp(-i \omega t) + A^*_{n'n} \exp(i \omega t) \quad ((11))$$

Using ((11)) in ((10)) one may readily integrate and find $b_{nn'}(t)$. In this case, $b_{nn'}(t)$ represents statistics based on time which try to resolve changes in time in $V(t)$. In such a case, $\exp(ipx)$ is not useful because it detects changes in space. One may note, however, that in this perturbation case, one must consider $\exp(-i e_n t)$ states, where e_n is full energy. Thus, it is $\exp(-i e_n t)$ with e_n being full energy of the H_0 eigenfunction which resolves changes in time. Different

W_n states resolve different changes in time just as different $\exp(ipx)$ s resolved changes in space.

The Case of Photon Absorption/Emission

Consider a single particle with possible energy levels E_n associated with $W_n(x)\exp(-iE_n t)$. $W_n(x)$ resolves space. If a photon is absorbed or emitted, both E_n and $W_n(x)$ change so resolution in both time and space changes. If one thinks of an average energy, then one considers an energy distribution. There are no changes in space and time to resolve as there is no $V(x)$ or $V(t)$. One simply has an average energy and possible E_n states and considers energy distribution with the least information possible which leads to Maxwell-Boltzmann type statistics. Thus, the spatial $\exp(ipx)$ or $W_n(x)$ space resolution interactions of the $\exp(-iE_n t)$ time change resolution from quantum mechanics seems to only be important if one resolves changes in time and space. Resolving changes in time and space means interacting with different points in time and space, hence interference. In the case of photon absorption/emission, one resolves nothing, but rather distributes energy as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann case, we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum mechanical free particle has two statistical distributions $\exp(-iet)$ and $\exp(ipx)$ where $e = \hbar^2 p^2 / 2m$. These two follow the Maxwell-Boltzmann condition of independence, i.e. $\exp(-e_1/T)\exp(-e_2/T) = \exp(-(e_1+e_2)/T)$. The two quantum statistics are associated with resolutions of space and time. In a two-slit experiment (or n-slit or diffraction from one slit), one resolves distances in space, i.e. there are impulse hits at different x points and interference of $\exp(ipx)$ type terms. Energy of each term does not change, nor does it change in a reflection-refraction problem which has momentum changes. Thus, it seems one may have statistics based on $\exp(ipx)$ and spatial resolution and independent $\exp(-iet)$ statistics in quantum mechanics based on time changes. We suggest that a perturbation potential of $V(t)$ shows how $\exp(-iet)$ is involved in resolving space whereas spatial resolution plays only a part in creating eigenfunctions of H_0 , the nonperturbative part of the Hamiltonian.

In the case of photon absorption/emission, one has neither spatial nor time resolution and simply uses energy distribution with minimum information and so obtains Maxwell-Boltzmann type factors. Interference in quantum mechanics seems to occur when one has either spatial or time resolution in a problem.

References

1. [https://phys.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Quantum_Mechanics/Essential_Graduate_Physics_-_Quantum_Mechanics_\(Likharev\)/06%3A_Perturbative_Approaches/6.05%3A_Time-dependent_Perturbations](https://phys.libretexts.org/Bookshelves/Quantum_Mechanics/Essential_Graduate_Physics_-_Quantum_Mechanics_(Likharev)/06%3A_Perturbative_Approaches/6.05%3A_Time-dependent_Perturbations)